

Implications of Flooding on Livelihoods and Sustainable Development in Kogi State

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ABSTRACT

The paper interrogated the impacts of flooding on the livelihoods in the Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. Apparently, climate change usually brings inauspicious atmospheric conditions to the Earth. One of the implications of climate change is flooding. On the other hand, flooding has several negative effects on human lives and livelihoods. It destroys crop production, trading, fishing, livestock production, transportation services and civil services, respectively. However, loss of businesses, loss of properties, loss of farmland, hunger and starvation, displacement from natural domains, high incidence of poverty, malaria and other diseases, damage to roads, loss of life and contamination of water are severe effects of flooding on livelihood activities, while environmental pollution can be regarded as a severe effect on the livelihood of the victims of flooding. The implications of these challenges on sustainable development can never be overemphasised. Yet, efforts to manage the causes of floods as well as ways to control them are still facing certain challenges in Kogi State and Nigeria in general. This study, therefore, utilises the focus group discussion approach of qualitative research to examine the issues therein. The findings revealed, among other things, that flooding has serious negative implications for the livelihoods of the people of the study area. Thus, the work recommended, among other things, that efforts to manage issues of climate change and flooding should be strengthened by both the government and citizens.

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1.1. Introduction

Floods are the most prevalent natural calamities confronting nations regardless of their state of development. The threat of floods is gradually growing the world over. Floods have a devastating effect on lifestyle as well as critical assets. Moreover, the relationship existing between flooding and food security took centre stage in global environmental and socioeconomic discourses. Floods are the most important and significant of all natural disasters, leading to fatalities globally. Doocy et al. (2013) averred that the danger of terrible losses experienced in the wake of a flood can be huge. Due to unmitigated deforestation coupled with unregulated human actions around coastal regions, river beds/basins, and lake areas. The effect of deluge events on the human population is assessed based on mortality rates, injury, displacement, hunger and other material losses (Pingali, 2005).

Also, after a considerable amount of time, increased mortality could also be recorded as a result of infectious diseases, which follows flood experience. Factors and conditions that lead to flooding are varied, complicated, and interconnected. These include weather and human factors. In terms of weather, the elements such as torrential rainfall, massive hurricanes, whirlwinds, whereas human factors include structural and infrastructural failures of levees and dams, modification of the landscape, which negatively prevent run-offs with waterproof surfaces, as well as poor drainage structures. Flooding has become a major issue of global concern, threatening human security, especially sustainable food production. In its recent report, the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk.

Reduction (UNISDR, 2015) compiled natural disasters across the globe from 1980 to 2011, and estimated a staggering figure of flood disasters at 3,455 with 2,689 storms, 470 droughts and 395 extreme temperatures. The report evidently depicts that floods have become one of the major causes of deaths associated with weather elements. Flood is increasingly becoming a threat to food security. Half of all flood-related deaths across the world have been found to occur in Asia (Doocy S. et al. 2013).

Worldwide, people often have many factors to struggle with in their livelihood activities, among which are natural disasters. The occurrence of natural disasters has been increasing over the years, resulting in loss of life, loss of businesses, damage to property and destruction of the environment. The number of people at risk has been growing each year, and most of them live in developing countries with high poverty levels, making them more vulnerable to disasters. (Living with- Risk 2006:6). The effects of natural disaster led to the disruption of the rural dweller's livelihood activities, causing a vicious circle of diminishing rural dwellers' incomes and adding to the risk, damage and stress of disaster (Kolawole, 2011).

The rural dwellers are more prone to natural disasters because they tend to live in marginal areas and depend on high-risk, low-return livelihood systems, such as rainy season agriculture, which also face many sources of vulnerability, including little physical infrastructures (Egboka, 2004). According to Egboka (2004), flooding is a natural process and can happen at any time in a wide variety of locations. It constitutes a temporary covering of land by water and presents a risk only when people, their property and/or environmental assets are present in the flood area (Adetunji and Oyeleye, 2013). Floods are part of people's lives in various regions of the world, recurring with varying magnitudes and frequencies to which people have adapted for centuries. These floods are generally expected and welcomed in many parts of the world, since they enrich the soil and provide both water and livelihoods (Brouwer et al., 2007).

A flood is described as an overflow of water that submerges land, low-lying villages and towns or an unusual condition affected by the inflow of the tide (Sivakumar, 2006). Flooding may occur as an overflow of water from water bodies, such as a river or lake, sea or large natural water basins. It may also occur due to an accumulation of rainwater on saturated ground in an aerial flood, thereby submerging land areas (Sivakumar, 2006; Carey, 2005). Flood takes place when ponds, riverbeds, soil and vegetation cannot absorb all the water, making excess water run off the land in volumes that cannot be carried within stream channels or retained in lakes, natural ponds or man-made

reservoirs. Flooding can be exacerbated by an increased amount of imperious surface or by natural hazards, such as fire or deforestation, which reduces the supply of vegetation that can absorb rainfall (Ayooso, 2012). The causes of flood

Climate change is making weather less predictable, especially in developing countries like Nigeria, where facilities to predict and manage weather conditions are not adequate (Gormerly, 2007). The unpredictability of rainfall in recent times has caused untold hardship during the rainy season (Greg, 2013). In the last quarter of 2022, to be specific, there have been incidences of heavy flooding in various parts of Nigeria that held the lives of the rural people at ransom and their assets, income, production activities, transport and health were automatically exposed to negative impacts. Such negative impact on human life should not be overemphasised, according to Ajibade et al. (2015), floods contributed one third of all deaths and one third of the loss of livelihood, which includes crop failure, loss of businesses and loss of houses, causing fatalities.

Flood menace has become a perpetual occurrence in Kogi state due to its geographical location at the confluence of the country's major rivers (River Niger- River Benue). Kogi state seriously experienced a flood disaster this year (2022), and the incident is beyond description, and it attracted humanitarian support from NEMA, Red Cross and many others. The flood affected five (5) local governments, which include Kogi (Koton Karfe), Lokoja, Bassa, Ajaokuta and Ibaji L.G.A of the State. In Kogi State, it is reported that up to 300,000 persons have been displaced, 30 persons were reported dead, thousands of hectares of farmland were destroyed, and livestock and fishery farms were charred away, especially in areas like Kogi local government. (NEMA 2022). Despite the economic damages and other negative effects caused by flood, it has been observed that there is no current study done on the effects of flooding on livelihood in the study area. It is based on this that this study is undertaken.

Climate Change and the Nigerian Environment

The 21st century is largely threatened by the problem of environmental degradation occasioned by climate change. Climate change is one of the greatest threats facing humankind today, and it has lots of implications for the survival of mankind. Hence, efforts geared towards environmental protection remain the main focus of most public discussion both locally and internationally. Evidence shows that the environment represents a wide range of external circumstances, conditions and the things that affect the existence and development of an individual, organism, group and/or society (Horton & McMichael, 2021).

No doubt, climate change is one of the most important environmental issues facing the world today, and Nigeria is not left out. The United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2014) defined Climate change as any significant change in the measures of climate lasting for an extended period of time. In other words, climate change includes major changes in temperature, precipitation, or wind patterns, among other effects, that occur over several decades or longer. Climate change, according to Omotosho(2015), is any long-term change in the patterns of average weather of a specific region or the Earth as a whole. It is an abnormal variation in the Earth's climate that usually occurs over durations ranging from decades to millions of years.

Ojomo, Elliot, Amjad and Bartram (2015) pointed out that climate change impacts pose great dangers with consequences such as desertification, sea level rise, flooding, water salination, among others. These impacts could manifest in food security challenges, damage to infrastructure and social dislocation. Additional impacts include threats to health as rising temperatures could bring about diseases such as chronic heat rashes, Cerebral-Spinal Meningitis (CSM), stroke, malaria and other related diseases. Climate change affects every citizen, every part of our environment and our natural resources, and thus practically every aspect of our lives, our economy, our urban and suburban development patterns (Omotosho,2015).

There are noticeable consequences of climate change in Nigeria, such as intense thunderstorms, widespread floods and incessant droughts. According to Borokinni(2017), the increased rate of climate change has severe consequences associated with it, such as desertification, drought, temperature rise, low agricultural yield, drying up of water bodies, and flooding, among others.

Flooding in Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State: An Evaluation of the Impacts on Livelihoods and Sustainable Development

During the Focus Group Discussion carried out in the course of this research, a number of findings emerged on the prevalent issues of flooding, causes of flooding, implications of flooding and efforts made by both government and NGO to curtail the impacts of flooding on people of Lokoja Local Government Area of Kogi State. One of the discussants, Adamu Illasu (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026), stated that Lokoja Local Government has witnessed occurrences and reoccurrences of flooding in the past few years. The causes of these challenges are strongly linked to climatic changes, rainfall, improper drainage, water release from the dam in Cameroon, and indiscriminate waste disposal.

Another discussant, Marriam Abdul (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026), supported that intense rainfall has been responsible for the flood experienced in Lokoja in recent years, particularly the intense one in the year 2012. This year, there was a heavy rainfall making Kanji Dam to become over-flooded. The dam was released, leading to overflow of water in the River Niger/Benue, which causes the flood.

It was also affirmed that heavy rainfall was responsible for flooding in Lokoja. Heavy rainfall is a derivative of global warming, thunderstorms and sea tidal surges. Another discussant, Suleiman Hussan (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026) stated that, “global warming was the major cause of flooding in the Lokoja Area of Kogi State.

All the above opinions seem to agree with the position of UNISDR (2015), which studied the causes of flooding in the United States using data on climate and field observation, and noted that floods can be caused by excess moisture resulting from continuous rainfall or snowmelts which exceeds natural river channel capacity. According to Green et al. (2006), rainfall and other climatic elements are generally responsible for floods, with rainfall being the primary and most important causative agent. Parry et al. (2004) also stated that floods are often secondary events of a climatic hazard such as tsunamis or hurricanes. Flooding linked to rivers occurs when the discharge from rivers increases, leading to saturation of the floodplain. When this occurs, such a river overflows its banks, leading to a flood at a stage referred to as the bank full stage. When

this combines with heavy rains, such flows turn torrential quickly. Urban area flooding has a lot to do with the geographical features of a location, such as being on a relatively flat terrain or a valley with inadequate drainage structure to prevent retention of moisture. When such a location, being an urban centre, is constrained by block drainages and inappropriate sewage disposal, flooding is always imminent. Urban flooding as a phenomenon is a regular occurrence in Nigeria, especially in cities such as Lagos, Warri, Ibadan, Aba and Maiduguri, among others. Raining seasons in Nigeria are characterised by gusts of wind as a result of tropical storms, leading to torrential rains with their attendant flash floods.

Based on this backdrop, the discussants were asked about the implications of flooding on the people. In response to this, a discussant named Ayodele Mark (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026) stated that the flood has greatly impacted the livelihoods and lives of the people of the area. Each of the times flood occurs in Lokoja, people loss farm land, crops, goods and even socio-economic activities are usually disrupted as a result of the flood in Lokoja. Hunger, starvation, displacement from natural domain, high incidence of poverty, contamination of drinking water, and health challenges are perceived as very severe effects of flooding on the livelihood of flood victims in Lokoja Local Government.

Queen Daniel (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026) supported that the flood has a great impact on the livelihoods of many people in the Lokoja Local Government Area of the state. It washed away farm lands, crops and put a stop to fishing activities across many communities in the Local Government. Similarly, floods have distracted businesses in the Local Government as markets were flooded, forcing the traders to move from the markets until the flood subsided.

Miechel Anthony (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026) noted that floods have led to loss of properties and business space. A number of people lost their properties while trying to escape from the flood. In the same vein, some businessmen who vacated their business spaces also lost ownership of the spaces at the end of the day.

Umar Yunusa (Focus Group Discussion 04/01/2026) positioned that floods have had serious negative impacts on both the livelihood of people and sustainable development in Kogi state. Affects the people's health, lives and resources, which are the basis for a true sustainable development. However, a number of efforts have been made by the government, individuals and NGO to relieve people from the impacts of the flood in Lokoja. This is in line with the principles of system theory, which underpins the study. According to the theory, everyone has a responsibility to contribute to the betterment of society, and each man's efforts must link with those of another man in order to achieve a given goal. In this regard, there have been response mechanisms put in place by different stakeholders, ranging from local to the Federal Government and its agencies. Provision of relief materials such as mattresses, bags of rice, and sanitary materials dominated the response mechanism by the Federal Government (NEMA) and other agencies. NEMA and some Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) often provide education on floods to the affected communities. The Cameroonian government provided money and seedlings for the farmers and medical attention to those who were displaced. After the 2012 floods, institutions and government agencies saw the need to put in place adequate flood prevention measures. Some well-meaning agencies also

contributed farming inputs to help farmers restart their lives after the devastating flood. One of the respondents explained: It is true when such things happen, they will not fold their arms and look. Government, NGOs and religious bodies will not fold their arms; everybody will come for assistance, and we appreciate all of them; they tried their best. As my people said and I, I saw that they provided relief materials like bed sheets, mattresses, foodstuffs, medical and also security. Like the issue of Banda that they said was cut off at that time, you can see how they build that place now. The village was not there before; they have now brought it to this side. You can see the embankment that the government is building now against such an oncoming flood. It's only God that is competent; whatever man does, just do it because of God. You will never praise a human being. But they tried their best in the distribution of the relief materials (Focus Group Discussion, 04/01/2026).

1.2. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study concludes that loss of businesses, loss of farms, loss of properties, hunger and starvation, displacement from natural domain, high incidence of poverty, ill health status of the flood victims, loss of life and causing damages on roads, contamination of drinking water were perceived as very severe effects of flooding on the livelihood of flood victims. While environmental pollution was perceived as a severe effect on the flood victims in the study area. The study therefore recommends that:

- i. Frequent workshops on climate change should be encouraged to help the victims in several ways of mitigating the effects.
- ii. Policy and protection should be put in place in case of adverse and unforeseen issues or circumstances.
- iii. The government, on the other way should put a compensation measure to aid the victims of climate change and also provide basic medical facilities at all levels in the affected areas to combat ill health issues in the areas.
- iv. Finally, more studies should be carried out on climate change and its implications in order to have empirical views on how the problems could be managed.

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